

PERCEPTION OF CHALLENGES FACED BY MOTHERS WHILE USING KANGAROO MOTHER CARE KIT IN PUBLIC HOSPITALS, LAHORE

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Abstract

Background: Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC) is a recognized method for promoting the health of preterm and low-birth-weight infants through continuous skin-to-skin contact and exclusive breastfeeding. The introduction of KMC kits aims to support mothers in practicing this technique more effectively.

Objective: The primary objective of this study was to explore mothers' experiences while using the KMC kit, specifically its effects on their mood, emotions, physical comfort, and bonding with their infants.

Methodology: A qualitative study was conducted among mothers practicing KMC with preterm and low-birth-weight infants. Data were collected through in-depth interviews. Transcripts were analyzed systematically to identify patterns, categories, and themes.

Results: Mothers reported challenges such as difficulty maintaining prolonged skin-to-skin contact, discomfort while breastfeeding, physical strain, and emotional stress during adaptation to KMC.

Conclusion: The study emphasizes the need for ongoing support, counseling, and practical guidance from healthcare providers to help mothers confidently practice KMC.

1. Introduction

Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC) was first introduced in 1978 in Bogotá, Colombia, as a response to overcrowded nurseries, limited incubator availability, and high neonatal mortality among low-birth-weight infants [1]. Global efforts led by organizations such as the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation and Save the Children have promoted KMC, yet differing healthcare capacities, cultural contexts, and inconsistent implementation remain challenges [2]. Preterm and low-birth-weight infants are at particularly high risk, with complications of prematurity accounting for a major proportion of neonatal deaths worldwide, especially in South Asia and

sub-Saharan Africa [3]. These infants often experience respiratory distress, developmental delays, feeding issues, and long-term cognitive or behavioral challenges, risks intensified by socioeconomic disparities [4]. Low-birth-weight infants represent a small proportion of newborns but contribute to a large percentage of neonatal mortality [5], leading the World Health Organization to recommend routine KMC for infants weighing less than 2000 g [6]. KMC offers a practical, cost-effective alternative to incubator care, particularly in resource-limited settings where essential neonatal equipment may be unavailable, difficult to maintain, or costly [7]. KMC promotes continuous skin-to-skin contact,

breastfeeding, maternal bonding, emotional security, stable temperature, weight gain, and reduced hospital stay and mortality [13–18]. Global initiatives, such as the Every Newborn Action Plan of 2014, aim to increase KMC coverage to improve newborn survival [8]. In Pakistan, neonatal mortality remains high, although gradual improvement has occurred in recent years [9–11]. With the establishment of KMC units, including the first UNICEF-supported unit in Lahore in 2016, training and practice have expanded but continue to face challenges [23].

Despite proven benefits, multiple barriers hinder KMC practice, including limited staff training, lack of community awareness, insufficient facility space, cultural norms, and household responsibilities [19–22]. The KMC kit, introduced to support safe skin-to-skin care, includes items such as gowns, infant clothing, hygiene supplies, and temperature-monitoring tools [24–25]. However, comfort, ease of use, privacy, mobility, and cultural acceptance influence mothers' willingness and ability to use the kit effectively. This study seeks to understand mothers' experiences with KMC and the KMC kit, identify challenges and cultural or environmental barriers, explore how these challenges affect KMC continuation, and inform healthcare providers about support needs to enhance successful implementation in Pakistan.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Design

This study employed a descriptive qualitative design to explore and describe mothers' experiences and perceptions while using the KMC kit. The focus was on understanding the challenges faced by mothers practicing Kangaroo Mother Care through their subjective accounts. Data were presented in narrative and observational form without statistical analysis.

2.2 Setting:

The study was conducted from January to September 2024 in two public hospitals in Lahore,

Pakistan: Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, which has a 7-bed Kangaroo Mother Unit, and Services Hospital, which has 6 KMC units integrated with neonatal and maternity care areas.

2.3 Sampling and Sample Size:

Purposive sampling was used to select mothers who were actively practicing KMC and using the KMC kit. A total of 13 mothers were interviewed, as data saturation was reached at that point.

2.4 Interview Guide Development:

Interview guidelines were created by the research team after reviewing relevant literature and conceptual mapping. The guide was developed in English, translated into Urdu, reviewed for clarity by experts, and approved. The questions addressed mothers' experiences, emotional responses, family and healthcare support, environmental conditions, and suggestions for improvement.

2.5 Data Collection:

Face-to-face semi-structured interviews were conducted with mothers in KMC units at both hospitals. Open-ended questions and probing techniques were used. Data collection included audio recordings, note-taking, photographs, and researcher observations.

2.6 Data Analysis:

Interviews were transcribed verbatim and translated into English. Transcripts were repeatedly reviewed to ensure accuracy. Data were read closely to identify patterns, which were organized into categories and sub-categories. Interpretation was guided by the research objectives and relevant literature. Themes were then developed to reflect mothers' experiences and challenges.

2.7 Ethical Considerations:

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, and participation was voluntary. The study adhered to ethical standards to ensure participant safety and dignity.

3. Results

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Demographic Data		n
Age	20-25 years	2 mothers
	26-30 years	6 mothers
	31-35 years	4 mothers
	36-40 years	1 mother
Mode of delivery	C-section	08
	SVD	05
Number of children	First child	09 mothers
	Fourth child	01 mother
	Second child	02 mothers
	Third child	01 mothers
Place of practicing KMC	Hospital A	5
	Hospital B	8
Place of living	Urban Lahore	12 mothers
	Rural Lahore	01 mother

A total of 13 mothers practicing Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC) participated in the study. Most mothers were between 26-30 years of age (n=6), followed by those aged 31-35 years (n=4), 20-25 years (n=2), and 36-40 years (n=1). The majority had delivered through cesarean section (n=8), while five had spontaneous vaginal deliveries (SVD).

In terms of parity, nine mothers were first-time mothers, two had two children, one had three children, and one had four children. Regarding the study setting, eight mothers were practicing KMC in Hospital B, while five were from Hospital A. Most participants were residents of urban Lahore (n=12), with only one mother belonging to a rural area.

Table 2 categories and sub categories of challenges representing mothers while using KMC kit

Categories	Subcategories
physical challenges	Comfort
	Discomfort
emotional challenges	Baby Safe or secure
	Initial fear
kit availability, size and stuff challenges	manage it alone
	Availability
	Size issues
	stuff dis comfortable

environmental challenges	Weather Space Privacy available Hygiene lighting
social challenges	Family support Husband support
health care providers challenges	Training support
practical challenges	Breastfeeding Baby care Toilet use
suggestions	Change stuff of kit Additional feature

Physical Challenges

Most mothers (11 out of 13) reported that the KMC kit was comfortable and easy to wear, contributing to a sense of physical ease during KMC. However, two mothers experienced discomfort due to the thick fabric, particularly in hot weather, and one mother reported discomfort due to the short length of the inner blouse. While the majority appreciated the kit’s support, heat and material thickness were the main concerns.

One mother shared, “Wearing this kit is very comfortable and makes me feel mentally relaxed because I know I am taking care of my baby.” (Mother 4 & Mother 9, first-time mothers)

In contrast, others noted weather-related discomfort: “The kit is easy to wear, but the material is thick, so I sweat in summer. Still, I wear it because it is good for my baby.” (Mother 5, fourth child; Mother 6, second child)

A few found the design uncomfortable: “The kit feels short and makes me self-conscious. It also causes heat and suffocation, especially in summer.” (Mother 2 & Mother 8, first-time mothers).

Emotional Challenges

All participants expressed emotional satisfaction and a strong sense of security and bonding while practicing KMC. Some mothers initially feared the baby might slip but stated this fear decreased over time with familiarity and confidence.

As one mother described, “At first, I was afraid the baby might fall, but with time that fear went away.” (Mother 1, first child)

Another emphasized emotional reassurance: “It is safe and secure. I feel very satisfied because my baby gains weight, maintains temperature, and is protected from infection. It is the best facility for preterm babies.” (Mother 2, first child).

Kit Availability, Size, and Stuff Challenges

Managing the Kit Alone

All mothers reported that they could manage the KMC kit independently, indicating that the kit’s design is user-friendly and does not require assistance for wearing or adjustment.

Kit Size and Material

The kit was generally described as easily available and suitable in size for most mothers. However, heat and sweating during summer emerged as a common challenge. Several mothers emphasized the need to improve the material to make it more breathable and comfortable in hot weather. Some also noted issues with fabric quality, tightness, and color fading.

For example:

“I can manage it alone; size is fine, but the material needs changes especially in summer.” (Mother 2, first child)

“Size is fine, but I felt sweating in hot weather; I even stitched another one at home.” (Mother 3, first child)

“Stuff is not good, its color fades and stains my skin.” (Mother 4, first child)

“Size is tight and I feel suffocation in hot weather.” (Mother 8, first child)

In contrast, a few mothers were satisfied:

“Size fits and the material is good to provide warmth; also, there is facility to bathe and change kit.” (Mother 9, first child)

“Size is fit and the stuff is comfortable for the baby’s warmth.” (Mother 10, first child; Mother 11, third child)

Environmental Challenges

Most mothers reported heat and sweating as the major environmental challenge while wearing the KMC kit, especially during summer. Despite discomfort, they continued KMC due to its importance for the baby. Privacy was generally described as adequate, though unclean washrooms and lack of fans made the environment less comfortable.

“I feel very hot and experience sweating and suffocation, but for my child, I do it happily.” (Mother 1, first child)

“Summer is not comfortable and washrooms are dirty, I fear germs may affect my premature baby.” (Mother 3, first child)

“Fans are not allowed, so I feel suffocation.” (Mother 10, first child)

Social Challenges and Support

All mothers reported strong family support, including help with meals and time to practice KMC. Husbands were supportive, though none wore the kit themselves.

“Family supports me and says baby is most important.” (Mother 2, first child)

“My husband supports me, even though he is out of the country.” (Mother 1, first child)

Healthcare Provider Support

Mothers consistently reported clear and helpful guidance from hospital staff through demonstrations and videos.

“Hospital staff guided me how to wear the kit through video and demonstration.” (All mothers)

Practical Challenges

Most mothers were able to manage daily tasks comfortably while wearing the kit. However, a few faced difficulty during breastfeeding, sometimes removing the baby from the kit.

“I can manage all tasks while wearing the kit; breastfeeding is easy.” (Mother 6, second child)

“I feel difficulty in breastfeeding, so I remove the baby from the kit.” (Mother 8, first child)

Benefits of KMC Kit

All mothers emphasized the health benefits for the baby, especially weight gain, temperature maintenance, and infection prevention.

“My baby’s weight increased from 1.62 to 1.92 kg.” (Mother 4, first child)

“It is the best facility in Pakistan for preterm babies.” (Mother 6, second child)

Suggestions for Improvement

The most common recommendation was to change the fabric to make the kit more breathable in summer. Some also suggested adding an extra feeding bottle to the kit.

“The stuff should be changed in hot weather.” (Mother 5, fourth child)

“There should be two bottles in one kit.” (Mother 1, first child).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study found that the Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC) kit plays an essential role in supporting preterm and low-birth-weight infants by promoting bonding, maintaining body temperature, and aiding weight gain. Mothers generally expressed emotional satisfaction and confidence while using the kit, recognizing its positive impact on their babies’ health. However, challenges were noted—particularly discomfort caused by heat due to the thick fabric, difficulty breastfeeding while wearing the kit for some mothers, and environmental issues such as inadequate ventilation and unhygienic washrooms. Despite these challenges, overall satisfaction remained high, demonstrating the strong acceptability and effectiveness of the KMC kit in public hospital settings.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that the KMC kit be improved by using lighter, breathable,

and moisture-absorbing fabric to make it more comfortable in hot weather, along with offering adjustable sizes and including an extra feeding bottle to support breastfeeding needs. Hospital environments should be strengthened by improving ventilation, ensuring regular cleaning of washrooms, and maintaining private spaces so that mothers can use the kit comfortably. Family awareness sessions should be arranged to increase the involvement of husbands and other family members, providing emotional and practical support to mothers. Additionally, ongoing hands-on training and guidance from healthcare providers, particularly on breastfeeding while wearing the kit, would help mothers overcome practical challenges and enhance their confidence in practicing Kangaroo Mother Care consistently.

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